

Transnational Access project QAD-DLR

1. General information

Project acronym QAD-DLR

Project title Quality of Airborne Data (QAD)

Type Training course

Scientific theme Quality assurance and intercomparison of airborne measurements

Main scientific field and Specific discipline Earth Sciences & Environment / Global change & Climate observation

Participants undertaking research

Name + link to id card	Research status	Email	Institution	Institution country	CV	Letter of reference	Publication
		Publication (1)					

Lead scientist's background

(scientific and aircraft measurements background and experience, English level) Dr. Radovan Krejci is currently research scientist at Department of Applied Environmental Science (ITM), Stockholm University, Sweden. He has more than ten years experience in airborne measurements of aerosol (number density, size distribution, volatility properties, light absorption and scattering) and cloud (CVI) microphysical properties using various airplanes, including German DLR Falcon 20, Dutch NLR Cessna Citation and Dornier 228 operated by AWI, Germany. He participated on several international projects including LBA-CALIRE, INDOEX, EU funded projects STREAM and INCA. Recently he participated on joint German-Japanese-Swedish projects ASTAR 2004 & 2007 and ANTSYO 2006-7 focused on airborne aerosol measurements in the Arctic and Antarctica, respectively. In addition he established in 2007 long-term aerosol observations at high altitude research station in Venezuelan Andes. Currently he is also leader of the airborne infrastructures work package within EU FP6 Integrated project EUCAARI. He is author and co-author more than 40 peer-reviewed papers.

Recent relevant publications by application group in last 5 years (up to 5)

- [List of Publications - Radovan Krejci](#)

Scientific problems being addressed by the experiments to be performed. Brief summary of the experiments The main theme of the training course is analysis and assessment of uncertainties and errors in measured properties using various research airplanes and instrumentation. An aircraft inter-calibration experiment is planned during the International Conference on Airborne Research for the Environment (ICARE) in Toulouse in October 2010. The integration of airborne observations involving multiple aircraft needs to consider the true uncertainties of the measurements on board of the different aircraft. In order to assess these errors during in-flight operating conditions, wingtip-to-wingtip comparison flights along constant level runs at various altitudes are a powerful tool. Almost every property of the atmosphere can be observed using different measurement techniques and/or different instrumentation. Assessing combined instrumental uncertainty, as well as temporal and spatial resolution is one of the key issues in data quality evaluation process.

Aircraft FA20 - DLR

Why this aircraft best suits the experiments? Proposed alternative aircraft For purpose of the QAD training course, results from ICARE intercomparison flights will be used. The actual list of airplanes will be identical to ICARE. Preliminary list of airplanes participating on ICARE is following:

Confirmed:

SAFIRE ATR42-320 F-HMTO
SAFIRE Falcon 20 F-GBTM
SAFIRE Piper Aztec F-BLEB
NERC Dornier-228 D-CALM
INTA CASA-212-200 EC-DUQ
KIT Schindler Enduro D-MIFU
METAIR Diamond HK36 TTC ECO HB-2335
FAAM BAE146 G-LUXE
AWI Basler BT-67 POLAR5 (DC-3T) C-GAWI

Expected:

DLR Falcon 20 D-CMET

Possible:

UNIMAN Cessna 182J G-AVCV

Verbally committed

2 x P3 Orion (NOAA and NRL) and the NSF C-130, both from USA.

In addition, QAD is open for other aircrafts and instrument providers.

2. Description of the experiments

Scientific objectives / Proposed work / Anticipated output The QAD training course will benefit from already planned and scheduled ICARE conference and air show, which will include extensive intercomparison measurements. The main topic of the QAD training course is to provide training on design, performance and data analysis of inter-comparison measurements among research airplanes. The course will include lectures as well as data analysis of inter-comparison data obtained during ICARE 2010 inter-comparison flights. The aircraft are equipped for all scientific purposes of the training course. Participants will learn how to design their own flight experiments within the "working" airspace available and visit the instrumented aircraft during the training course. When possible, participants will be taken on-board during the intercomparison flights or they will be able to follow a live video transmission available during the ICARE intercomparison flights.

The target audience of this training course is:

- 1) early-stage researchers (PhD students and post-docs) with a focus on airborne measurements
- 2) professionals working in airborne research field
- 3) limited number of university lecturers.

The participants of the QAD training course will be selected based on their merits, stage in their carrier and short scientific proposal about the measurements to be performed and related research questions. Overall the group of selected participants should form a suitable mix of candidates according to target groups mentioned above.

In preparation of the inter-calibration experiment the instrument operators report the nominal values of the precision and accuracy for the measurements to be compared. During the experiment calibration standards will be compared first at the ground as far as possible. Airplanes equipped with real-time data link will transmit measured data on-line. Those without this equipment will transfer measured data shortly after landing. Students will then analyse quality of the intercomparison measurements under guidance of professionals and lecturers. Report from participants will form final output of the QAD training course.

Weather conditions (e.g. clouds, atmospheric stability, wind speed and direction, weather...) Clear sky conditions

Time constraints (time of the day, pass(es) of satellites, weekends, season...) fully depending on the ICARE intercomparison scheme

Location(s) and reason for that choice Map of general area: [Project QAD: Map of general area](#)

the same as for ICARE intercomparison. Air space available for intercomparison flights south of Toulouse is marked in purple.

Number of flights / flight hours and flight patterns no special requests in addition to the ICARE intercomparison flights. As suggestion, approach used during previous intercomparisons (AMMA, EUCAARI) can form a basis for general flight pattern.

Each aircraft pair inter-compared the measurements along two to three different flight levels of a least 20 min duration. Lowermost level should be close to ground at approximately 300 m. Second level close to top of boundary layer (BL), third layer at max altitude available in free troposphere. In case that only two level comparison will be possible, then first two flight levels in the BL should be reduced to one. The aircraft joining formation will hold position just behind on the right hand side of the lead aircraft with a separation of about 150 ft.

For one reference fast flying airplane (DLR Falcon 20) and one slow flying airplane (one of the following: INTA CASA, SAFIRE Piper Aztec or NERC Dornier 228) approx. 6 flight hours are planned. For the rest of the participating aircrafts 3 flight hours per airplane are requested.

Other constraints or requirements Participants of the QAD training course should have an opportunity to join intercomparison flights on board of the airplanes when possible.

3. Key measurements required to achieve science aims

Parameter / measurement required The final list of measurements used for intercomparison and data quality analysis and training will be finalized prior the ICARE depending on number and type of the airplanes present and instrumentation on board. At this point following list of parameters is proposed:

static pressure
temperature
horizontal and vertical wind
turbulence
H2O mixing ratio
ozone mixing ratio
CO mixing ratio
aerosol number density
aerosol size distribution (PCASP, FSSP300)
aerosol optical properties (absorption, scattering)

If applicable, specify TA instrument required None

Instruments to be provided by hosting aircraft operator (basic instrumentation owned by the aircraft operator described on EUFAR website only) depending on final payload on board of each of the aircrafts joining the ICARE.

Instruments to be provided by scientific group (*Have already been flown. On which aircraft? Do the instruments have their own data acquisition system?*) no

Instrument operators onboard (in addition to those provided by the aircraft operator). If so, how many?

If applicable, plans for simultaneous field work plans / ground equipment to be used no

4. Data processing and analysis

Methodology for handling the data and analysis of output (*airborne data acquisition, ground-truthing / observations, data processing and interpretation*) In order to perform a double blind data comparison, the results will be uploaded to a dedicated place by each instrument operator as soon as possible after the intercomparison flights. Then participants of the course will perform the analysis of measured parameters and write a short report.

Resources available to support the project beyond the flying/data acquisition period (*funding, cooperation with other projects, manpower for analysis of results and preparation of user report, availability of laboratory facilities...*) An Auditorium or class room as well as computer room, both for 20-30 persons
approximately 10 lecturers
accommodation in Toulouse
bus transfer to and from the airport for intercomparison flights

5. Planning

Starting date: 26-10-2010

Ending date: 05-11-2010

Preferred and acceptable dates (*season / time windows*) 26 October - 5 November 2010

Agreement to share aircraft time (*project clustering, cost sharing*) Yes

6. Other useful comments

Training benefit of the project (*e.g. spread potential of airborne research to a wide scientific community; training of research students in experimental planning, methodology, data analysis and applications, etc*) Spread potential of airborne research to a wide scientific community. Data quality and assurance represent the core of data analysis and reliability of airborne data for consequent use by scientists in their work. Thus, there is need not only to process airborne data correctly, but also as much as possible in a unified way allowing easier and transparent future use of measured data from various research airplanes. The QAD training course provides very good opportunity to establish such level in data quality and assurance of airborne measurements within EUFAR community with impact well beyond scale of EUFAR fleet. The participants will also gain experience in proper design of intercomparison measurements and methodology.

The results and reports from QAD training course will be available to EUFAR community on EUFAR website.

If possible, 3 scientific reviewers that EUFAR may contact Dr. A. Robert MacKenzie, University of Lancaster, UK
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Prof. Dr. Klaus Pfeilsticker, Institut für Umweltphysik, University of Heidelberg
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Sources of funding of the project and of related projects (*if clustering with existing projects supported either by national or other EC funding, how the project add additional or complementary aims to the already funded experiments*) fully funded by EUFAR

Scientific training provided by lead scientist to other EUFAR sponsored scientists within the fields of the proposed experiments and analysis Yes

Number of students 20

Number of days recommended 14

Knowledge about EUFAR opportunities from From your colleagues

Related documents

You may need to login to the EUFAR Back Office to see all the documents.

- [Flyer Training Course QAD](#)
- [FP7-N5ET meeting 01: Project QAD](#)
- [QAD: Airborne Radiation Measurements: Methods and Instruments](#)
- [QAD: Atmospheric Aerosol Measurements by Research Aircraft](#)
- [QAD: Chemical Observations of the Atmosphere](#)
- [QAD: Final Presentation - Group 1](#)
- [QAD: Final Presentation - Group 2](#)

- [QAD: Final Presentation - Group 3](#)
- [QAD: Group Picture](#)
- [QAD: In-flight Measurement Intercomparison](#)
- [QAD: Intercomparison flight picture](#)
- [QAD: Meteorological Measurements](#)
- [QAD: N5 Education and Training](#)
- [QAD: Scientific Group Report Template](#)
- [QAD: Techniques for In-situ Airborne Measurements of Cloud Properties](#)